

Responsible research and innovation approach for transitioning the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories

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INTRODUCTION

The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach aims to encourage societal actors to work together during the whole research and innovation (R&I) process to better align R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society. Experience shows that strategies and practices based on RRI can open R&I to all relevant actors, and improve co-operation between science and society, fostering the recruitment of new talent, and pairing scientific excellence with social awareness and responsibility.

Territories have a specific advantage to address the complexity of the challenges set by the interplay between science and society. Indeed, local actors have an intimate knowledge of the physical territorial setting, and local ecology, i.e. the status quo of the complex relationships between cultural, social, economic and political actors, of the local dynamics, history, expectations and requirements as well as specific concerns. Territories can work towards the establishment of self-sustaining R&I ecosystems that are characterised by a high degree of openness, democratic accountability, and responsiveness to need by taking action to promote all parts of RRI (i.e. gender equality, science education, open access/open data, public engagement, and ethics).

This requires them to bring relevant R&I actors together, for instance citizens and civil society organisations (CSOs), universities, research institutions, formal and informal education institutions (including primary and secondary schools), governments and public authorities (including regional and local administrations and science policy institutions), businesses (including industry, the service sector and

social entrepreneurs) and science mediators. New R&I working methods within and between organisations, including novel and transparent governance relations, would promote greater sustainability and inclusiveness at local, national, EU and global levels.

Consortia are expected to elaborate and implement a more open, transparent and democratic R&I system in their defined territories, to evaluate their activities, and provide evidence of societal, democratic, environmental, economic and scientific impacts. Involvement in the project should have a measurable transformative and opening effect on organisations involved; this should be sustainable (i.e. last beyond the lifetime of funding), for instance through the introduction of new forms of decision making, development of business plans or co-operation agreements, and institutional changes in participating organisations.

DigiTeRRI faces a new challenge by applying RRI principles within the territorial digitalisation processes. Territories cope with a deep transformation relating to digitalisation. Companies must integrate new technologies, e.g. robots, automatic production lines, sensors, etc. that impact their relations with customers and suppliers, change the required skills of employees and highlight new forms of management. Public institutions must design new services while integrating users with changing needs. Entertainment activities get digital. And everywhere, the digital divide is threatening. Even local and regional democracy is impacted. Our objectives are to elaborate and experience RRI approaches regarding digitalisation.

EVIDENCE AND ANALYSIS

DigiTeRRI brings together representatives from quadruple helix actors, namely industry & business, science & research, government & public administration, and civil society in three territories implementing an RRI approach. The roadmap development in DigiTeRRI takes place in co-creation workshops with the afore mentioned actors, the representatives of quadruple helix actors. The involved territories in DigiTeRRI (Styria in Austria, Grand Est in France, and Värmland in Sweden) have developed several formats for communicating with the stakeholders and in their territories. By means of round tables for industry & business, or for universities & research organisations, or for government & public administration, and civil society the RRI approach and the transition into a digitalised territory is debated so that the awareness for it can grow. Therefore, each territory has organised web meetings in specific formats with representatives of these actor types (a) to impart the RRI approach, (b) to discuss RRI and its meaning for the territory, (c) to develop a vision for digitalisation in the territory with RRI approach.

The mapping provides a solid – both quantitative and qualitative – empirical analysis of scientific research, science-industry collaboration and technological development, as well as a broad range of digitalisation support measures („digital practices“) in Grand Est, Styria and Värmland. We find that digitalisation is a ubiquitous and major concern in these territories, whereby the focus is on the enabling role of digital technologies for innovation in the traditional sectors. Main drivers of digitalisation activities are both industry (Grand Est, Styria) and university (Värmland). Industrial clusters and international networks are abundant, but a major challenge seems to be the interface between national and regional institutions: While the European Union has successfully introduced flexibility at the regional level with its Smart Specialization approach, the institutional setup is often governed by the national level, which may lead to inefficiencies regarding the advancement of RRI aspects during the digital transformation of the territories.

Across the territories, a total of 36 digital practices was identified and analysed in the areas of education, innovation and technology development, provision of infrastructure, territorial development as well as work and employment. The figure on the next page gives and overview.

Building on the status of the three territorial R&I ecosystems, visions for each territory were created with the integration of the RRI aspects. These build the basis for the next steps in the roadmapping process and first actions and goals for digitalisation in the territories. The work done in recent months has unveiled that the implemented methodologies opens the “borders” between the organisation types such as research and public administration, or public administration and industry, and even more, has opened the collaboration between all four quadruple helix representatives. The activities in the territories have initiated a transparent and democratic approach for working together, for co-creating their future.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Unifying all affected stakeholders through consideration of the quadruple helix creates a strong driving force in a transformation process. Creating a common picture in a specific vision in a territory encourages the interest and commitment of all those concerned releasing incredible innovative potential. Starting point for all transformative processes is to build a common vision, a picture of the future together.

- Considering the quadruple helix for stakeholder involvement ensures that different viewpoints and considerations are brought into the discussion, namely from industry & business, university & research, government & public administration, and civil society. It is the responsibility of policy to foster stakeholder involvement by e.g. promoting activities or projects with active involvement of stakeholders taking the quadruple helix or similar concepts into account.
- Through stakeholder engagement and integration of all partners of the quadruple helix new interfaces became visible or were created. These bridges were taken up in the DigiTeRRI territories and more intense RRI round tables were organised. This ensured communication in smaller groups establishing common sense of co-creation while strengthening trust across these interfaces.
- This project reinforces links between stakeholders and creates new kinds interactions between quadruple helix actors.

- The territories learn from their differences in geography, size, type of industry, relationship with stakeholders, and on how they deal with the topic of RRI and the initiatives in place.
- Promoting all parts of RRI (i.e. gender equality, science education, open access/open data, public engagement, and ethics) supported the territories on their way to a transformation towards digitalisation that is characterised by a high degree of openness, democratic accountability, and responsiveness. Taking the RRI principles (inclusiveness, anticipation, reflexivity, responsiveness) into account from the beginning of the visioning process is seen as an indispensable benefit for the process and highly recommended.
- Round tables organised for specific groups are a valuable instrument in regional communication and for building links between RRI concepts and stakeholder groups, including public policy. Integration of quadruple helix stakeholders in the decision-making process is strongly recommended for territorial transition processes.
- Raising RRI awareness at regional level is a profound condition for activities including or facing at RRI aspects.
- RRI allows to link subjects that are treated separately and to have a global vision of a responsible approach (e.g. gender balance linked to digital schools, ethic with AI etc.).

SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY

The DigiTeRRI project can be considered as a toolkit itself. DigiTeRRI epitomizes a strategic methodology, namely roadmapping. Roadmapping was selected because first actions should already be implemented during the project duration and roadmapping allows this. This roadmapping process takes place for territories, for innovation ecosystems, in three different countries. Since innovation systems are complex systems DigiTeRRI has to deal with these versatile systems. The roadmapping process starts with stocktaking and mapping to describe the current situation and the starting point for the next steps, thus creating common understanding among the involved stakeholders. The visioning process as the second phase unifies the stakeholders and leads to mutual orientation. For even broader commitment in the territories, additional round table discussions support the co-creation in the territories. The third phase is the roadmap development in a co-creation process in the territories followed by the last phase, the implementation of the first actions developed in the process.

All phases are embedded into a common framework, which incorporates RRI into the digitalisation of traditional industry territories. The framework is intended for territories that have adopted a smart specialization strategy (S3). The framework highlights RRI-related challenges and opportunities arising from digitalisation. All the tools and framework developed in the DigiTeRRI project will be made available during the project as open access material.

The figure on the left side shows which RRI policies are pursued by local decision makers in the digitalisation processes.

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PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

The project DigiTeRRI elaborates a framework and develops a roadmap for a responsible transition of traditional industry regions into digitalised industrial self-sustaining R&I ecosystems by RRI approach for three territories in Europe, Värmland in Sweden, Région Grand Est in France, and Styria in Austria. The project addresses the complexity of the challenges in the interplay between science, industry, government, and society (quadruple helix) in the defined territories. Quadruple helix stakeholders of the three partner territories are actively engaged in this project. DigiTeRRI targets the following objectives:

- Characterising and mapping the current three territorial R&I ecosystems: The statuses of their R&I ecosystems, of their digitalisation degrees, and their statuses regarding RRI is evaluated and characterised. The empirical analysis is also visualised.
- Generating a vision for each of the three territories: Each of the three territories co-creates a vision for the transition into a digitalised territory by RRI approach with representatives from the quadruple helix.

- Developing a roadmap for transitioning into responsible digitalised territories: A roadmap for the digitalisation with RRI approach for each of the three territories is developed by means of co-creation with stakeholders (representatives of quadruple helix actors). This process considers the domains knowledge & skills (education regarding technology, software development, data computing, but also web marketing, new business models for high education but also how to use internet for uneducated people), technology (access to and developing new), networks & collaboration (inside the territory and worldwide, e.g. how to build global digital value chains), infrastructure (e.g. broadband, 5G), culture & values (open for the change, ethics, etc.), leadership (how an organisation can take over the lead for the transition process in the territory), communication.
- Implementing transitioning activities: The actions developed in the roadmap process are implemented towards a more open, transparent and democratic digitalised R&I ecosystem by considering various policy instruments, defined during the roadmap process.

The applied methodology is a roadmapping process summarised in the following figure.

PROJECT IDENTITY

PROJECT NAME	Responsible Research and Innovation Approach for Transitioning the Traditional Industry Regions into Digitalised Industry Territories (DigiTeRRI).
COORDINATOR	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, AIT; Vienna; Austria; marianne.hoerlesberger@ait.ac.at
FUNDING SCHEME	H2020-SwafS-2018-2020, SwafS-14-2018-2019 (Supporting the development of territorial Responsible Research and Innovation)
DURATION	January 2020 - December 2022 (36 months).
BUDGET	€2,004,037.50
WEBSITE	https://digiterri.eu/
FOR MORE INFORMATION	Contact: Marianne Hörlesberger, AIT, marianne.hoerlesberger@ait.ac.at

FURTHER READING

- Deliverable D2.3 “Description of the R&I ecosystem landscape of each of the three territories” (public) presents the methodology and data of the mapping and unveils the strengths of the territory with regard to digitalisation, whereas the data taken from scientific literature databases, patents, and EU projects.
- Deliverable D2.4 “Regional-specific transition practices” describes already detected RRI aspects in the three territories.
- Deliverable D3.2 “Framework for RRI implementation in R&I ecosystems of the three territories” (public) gives a good overview about the DigiTeRRI approach.
- The DigiTeRRI concept will be presented at STS conference in Graz, Austria, 3-5 May 2021 (STS - STS Conference Graz (tugraz.at))

DigiTeRRI project is at the end of the first year and therefore, there will be, of course several publications and conference contributions.

CONSORTIUM

AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Innovation Systems & Policy, Vienna, Austria;
Grand E-Nov, European Affairs Department, Strasbourg, France;
Karlstads Universitet, Grants and Innovation Office, Karlstad, Sweden;
MATERIALIA, -, Metz, France;
Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Industrial liaison, Leoben, Austria;
Nordlandforskning AS, Innovation & Entrepreneurship, Bodø, Norway;
Standort und Marketing Bruck an der Mur, -, Bruck an der Mur, Austria;
The Paper Province Ekonomisk Foerening, -, Karstad, Sweden;
Universite de Lorraine, ERPI Laboraory, Nancy, France
Värmlands Läns Landsting, Regional Growth Department, Karlstad, Sweden;
WeDo Project Intelligence Made Easy, -, Barcelona, Spain;
Zentrum für angewandte Technologie Leoben, -, Leoben, Austria.

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